

Predicting Heart Ailment using Jupyter

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Abstract—The heart is more important to the human body than any other circulatory organ. Its characteristic is to provide and pump blood to other organs and the brain. So, it's far very critical to have a healthy heart however researchers discovered the risk of heart failure increases each day. Many heart specialists can diagnose coronary heart sickness with their enjoy and competencies. However, some professionals missing the expertise or expertise to are expecting cardiovascular ailment inside the early stages, a small mistake can price a patient's life. consequently, it is vital to apply particular methods and algorithmic tools to estimate the occurrence of cardiac problems inside the early degrees. They compare the likelihood of heart disease in a person and look for targets to focus on. Typically, it takes years of experience and a battery of medical examinations. The primary purpose of the paintings in this study is to find the best typeset of rules for showing maximum accuracy. Decision tree and Logistic Regression are used to broaden the prediction system if you want to Analyze and expect the opportunity of a coronary heart ailment.

Keywords—Data Mining, Classification, Prediction, Heart Ailment, Jupyter

I. INTRODUCTION

The heart is more important than any other circulatory organ to the human body. Its job is to bring blood to the brain and other organs and pump it out. As a result, having a healthy coronary heart is critical, but researchers discovered that the chance of coronary heart failure is rising every day. With their experience and capabilities, several cardiac specialists can identify coronary heart disease. However, if a few physicians lack the intelligence or understanding to diagnose cardiovascular disease in its early stages, even a minor error can have a major influence on a patient's lifestyle. Consequently, it's critically essential to use specific methods and algorithmic equipment to estimate the prevalence of cardiac issues in the early stages. They compare the likelihood of coronary heart disease in a person by examining the goals that they are aiming after. Years of training and a thorough clinical test may be necessary. The primary objective of this study project is to find the unique set of rules that would provide the highest level of accuracy. If you need to analyze and count on the chance of coronary heart illness, you can use a decision tree and Logistic Regression to produce a prediction device.

Heart disease symptoms vary greatly depending on the type of difficulty a person is experiencing. A few signs are difficult for the typical individual to recognize. Typical indications and symptoms include chest discomfort, dyspnea, and coronary heart palpitations. Angina, or angina pectoris, is a type of chest discomfort that happens when a portion of the heart no longer receives adequate oxygen. It is frequent in

many types of coronary heart disease. Angina can be brought on by traumatic events or physical activity, and it usually lasts less than 10 minutes. Health issues can also develop as a result of rare forms of coronary heart disease. The symptoms of a coronary heart attack are similar to those of angina, except that they can appear at any time during rest and are more severe. The signs and symptoms of a heart attack can sometimes be mistaken for indigestion. Heartburn, stomach discomfort, and a heavy feeling in the chest are all possible symptoms. Other indications and symptoms of a heart attack include discomfort that moves throughout the body, such as from the chest to the palms, neck, back, stomach, or jaw, dizziness, lightheadedness, as well as copious sweating.

To produce predictions in this study, a comparative comparison of the two data mining classification techniques, Decision Tree and Logistic Regression, is used. The analysis is done at several levels of cross-validation and several percentages of percentage split evaluation methods respectively. In this study, the "Heart Disease" dataset from the UCI machine learning repository was used to make heart disease predictions. We must determine which of the two methods, Logistic Regression, and Decision Tree, will provide the most accurate results. And finally, we can understand using which algorithm has the best accuracy in the prediction of heart diseases.

II. METHODOLOGY

Fig.1. The research work's methodology

The strategy indicated in Fig. 1 for constructing the classification model needed to predict heart disease in

patients can be used to predict heart disease. The model serves as a foundation for doing cardiac disease prediction using machine learning approaches. To make predictions, a classifier must first be trained using the records, after which a classification model must be created, which is then fed with a fresh unknown record and a prediction made. The Performance Evaluation of the two classification algorithms is part of the study approach. The training portion of this study involves using the heart disease dataset to train two classification methods, Decision Tree and Logistic Regression, and then creating a classification model.

A. Dataset Description

This study was based on the "Heart Disease" dataset from the UCI machine learning library. Despite the fact that this database has 76 features, all published studies only employ a subset of 14 of them. The Cleveland database, in particular, is the only one that machine learning researchers have used thus far. The "target" field shows whether the patient has heart illness or not. It ranges from 0 (no presence) to 4 (present). The purpose of this research is to find a way to anticipate heart illness regardless of the type. A numeric data type that ranges from 29 to 77 years old is used to represent the patient's age. Figure 2 depicts all of the properties and their values.

Sl.No	Attribute name	Description
1	age	Age in year
2	sex	1=male; 0=female
3	cp	Chest pain
4	trestbps	Resting blood pressure
5	chol	Serum cholesterol in mg/dl
6	fastgls	Fasting blood sugar & gt ; 1= true ; 0= false
7	restecg	Resting electrocardiographic result
8	thalach	Maximum heart rate achieved
9	exang	Exercise induced angina 1= yes ; 0 = no
10	oldpeak	ST depression induced by exercise relative to rest
11	slope	The slope of the peak exercise ST segment(1-3)
12	ca	Number of major vessels(0-3) colored by flourosopy
13	thal	The defect type of the heart 3= normal ; 6= fixed defect ; 7= reversible defect
14	target	0= do not have heart disease ; 1= have heart disease

Fig.2. Attribute and Description of the dataset used for research

B. Statistical Analysis

Kaggle.com was used to acquire the data. The dataset was then downloaded and saved in Microsoft Excel as a CSV file, which was then used for data analysis. The UCI machine learning repository's "Heart Disease" dataset.

Fig.3. Dataset

C. Tool used – Jupyter

Project Jupyter develops open-source software, open standards, and interactive computing services in a variety of programming languages. Jupyter Notebook is a web platform that lets you create and share code, graphics, and text documents. It can be used for data science, statistical modeling, machine learning, and other applications.

C.1. Installing Jupyter

Fig.4.1. Anaconda installation.

Fig.4.2. License Agreement.

Fig.4.3. Select installation type

Fig.4.4. Select a place for installation.

Fig.4.5. Options for advanced installation

Fig.4.6. Installing

Fig.4.7. Anaconda3

Fig.4.8. Completing Anaconda3 2021.11 setup

III. PERFORMANCE METRICS

This section explains the metrics that were utilized in the research.

A. Precision

Precision refers to the proportion of important occurrences found between the retrieved instances.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$$

B. Recall

The recall is the small percentage of appropriate examples that have been retrieved out of the total amount of relevant examples. The recall Eq. is given.

$$\frac{TP}{TP + FN} = \text{Recall}$$

C. F Score

The real positive rate (recall) and precision are weighted averaged.

$$MCC = \frac{TP \times TN - FP \times FN}{\sqrt{(TP + FP)(TP + FN)(TN + FP)(TN + FN)}}$$

IV. OVERVIEW OF DATA MINING TOOLS

Data mining has a wide range of applications, ranging from marketing and advertising for goods, functions, and products to artificial intelligence research, biological sciences, crime investigations, and high-level government intelligence.

- Here in the above picture, the basic libraries are imported.
- The dataset is named “heart.csv”.
- `df = PD.read_csv(“heart.csv”)`
code is used to read the dataset.
- `df.head()`
is used to explore the data set.
- `df.shape`
is used to know the data sets rows and columns

Fig.5.4

- To get the description of the given dataset.

Fig.5.5

- Finding the correlation among the attributes.

Fig.5.6

- To get the Cross Table.

Fig.5.7

Fig.5.8

- For scaling the data.

Fig.5.9

- For checking the sample size.
- Using the Logistic Regression algorithm to predict the heart disease from the given data set.

Fig.5.10

- Using the algorithm to find the accuracy.

Fig.5.11

- Using the Decision Tree algorithm to predict heart disease from the given data set.
- Using the algorithm to find the accuracy.

Fig.5.12

- When comparing both the algorithm. Logistic Regression has more accuracy than Decision Tree.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Finally, the Logistic Regression classification technique holds up well in the study of medical data classification, particularly for heart illnesses, in terms of performance and accuracy.

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